

THE EURO-GLOBAL PLATFORM FOR MECHANISM-BASED DRUG REPURPOSING

From imprecise drug therapy
to precision medicine

Funded by
the European Union

A NEW ERA FOR DRUG REPURPOSING

Mechanism-based drug repurposing will revolutionize the way we approach drugs.

It will help us find **new uses** for already registered drugs, increase **precision** & radically cut down on **costs** and time in the drug development process.

Ultimately, this paradigm shift will streamline the transition to **clinical trials** that are fit-for-purpose, innovation-driven & compliant with the highest standards in **safety** & operational **excellence**.

**NEW DISEASE
DEFINITIONS**

**NETWORK
PHARMACOLOGY**

**ORGAN-AGNOSTIC
MEDICINE**

**PRECISION
MEDICINE**

WHAT WE DO

REPO4EU is building a **unique platform for drug repurposing**, pooling **stakeholders & expertise** globally to create a fully-fledged, made in Europe **infrastructure** for drug repurposing

BIOINFORMATICS

In silico disease
modelling
Virtual patient
Artificial Intelligence

REPURPOSING

Mechanism-based drug
repurposing
De novo signaling module
construction

A PARADIGM SHIFT

Focus on point of care diagnostics
for patient stratification &
precision therapy
Less animal work

OUR PROPOSITION

REPO4EU's ultimate goal is to host & grow a **EU industry-level online platform** for **validated precision drug repurposing** with a global reach.

This platform will operate as a **data hub** for key **information, training** resources, **matchmaking** & **collaboration** in drug repurposing.

Digital biomarkers & AI models for patient stratification

Ethics & data protection, patents, freedom to operate & a global **HTA** database

2D & 3D drug printing for GMP-compliant repurposing at any dose

Innovative **phase I/II trials** in hypertension, diffuse-intrinsic pontine glioma & thyroid carcinoma

THE PLATFORM

A SUSTAINABLE MODEL & PRIORITY SELECTION MECHANISMS

Integrating the scientific, methodological, financial, legal, regulatory & IP dimensions of drug repurposing

THE GO-TO EU REPOSITORY FOR DRUG REPURPOSING

Enabling & facilitating seamless access, pooling & sharing of top-quality data assets in drug repurposing

AN ONLINE & MULTIDISCIPLINARY INNOVATION HUB

A virtual, connected community in drug repurposing to foster collaboration, networking & knowledge transfer

LET'S TALK DRUG REPURPOSING

REPO4EU is a EU-funded initiative that brings together **28 partners** from **10 countries** worldwide. We have the experts & the experience to help you...

Secure **bioinformatics support** for an unmet medical need

Explore a **registered compound** or a specific **mechanism**

Locate a **clinical trial test site** for phase I-III

Assess your **freedom to operate**

Outline a **patenting** strategy or browse **regulatory advice**

Network or develop a **business plan**

Visit us at repo4.eu

KEEP IN TOUCH!

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